

Potential deployment of reversible solid-oxide cell systems to valorise organic waste, balance the power grid and produce renewable methane: a case study in the Southern Italian Peninsula

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A.A., L.W., M.P., Y.Z. and S.Y. involved in funding acquisition, designed the research Project and the overall methodology; C.C., A.A. and F.G. analysed power generation and load data; N.P. and V.M. performed the biomass assessment in Italy; C.C. and A.A. wrote the paper. All authors contributed to the final review and editing.

Keywords

SOFC (solid oxide fuel cell), SOEC (Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell), Biomethane production, Waste valorization, Grid Adequacy, Hydrogen, Renewable energy resources

Abstract

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A large market penetration of non-dispatchable renewable power sources (vRES), i.e. wind and photovoltaic, may be hampered by an increasing need for large scale energy storage capacity and challenges in power grid balancing. Novel technologies integrating waste gasification with reversible Solid-Oxide Cell (rSOC) systems are proposed to provide flexible grid balancing services. The rSOC system operated in electrolysis mode uses excess power from vRES to generate hydrogen (H₂) which is combined with syngas derived from waste gasification to produce methane (CH₄). The rSOC system can also be operated in fuel cell mode by oxidising syngas to produce electricity. In this work a methodology aimed at estimating the potential deployment of the rSOC technology in a future power system dominated by intermittent renewables is developed. The hourly power grid residual loads (i.e. the difference between load and vRES power generation) and the low-grade organic waste and residues availability, were quantified and matched for the southern Italian peninsula in 2030. The results show that the theoretical grid flexibility needs - about 10 TWh of overproduction and 5 TWh of underproduction in 2030 - might be fully satisfied with the complete disposal of the municipal organic waste generated in 2030 (6.7 Mt) and the production of 1.4–2.4 Mt of renewable CH₄, pointing to an intriguing perspective for the deployment of rSOC systems at large scale. The multifunctionality of the system proposed is an added value that can make it a convenient and efficient piece of the puzzle of technologies to invest in a climate-neutral and circular economy. The results and methods here presented are ultimately to be intended as the basis for the estimations of future potential deployment and economic and environmental assessments of competing technologies.

Contribution to the field

The transition towards a climate neutral energy system requires higher penetration of non-dispatchable renewables energy resources. The European Union aims at achieving a 96–99% renewable energy share in power sector by 2050 (EU energy roadmap 2050). We propose the deployment of the W2G rSOC system to enable such a renewables penetration in the power sector. The W2G technology is a win-win-win technology which may dispose of the organic waste, balance the power grid and produce methane. Our research question is 'what is the potential deployment of the W2G technology'. To answer that question we needed to answer also the questions 'what is the balancing need of the power grid in 2030?' and 'what is the availability of biowaste in 2030?' We develop a methodology to estimate the hourly grid flexibility needs in a future power system dominated by intermittent renewables, geographically explicit availability, and costs of sustainable organic waste streams, compatible with the W2G technology and apply it to a specific case study. We provide data and methods for future assessments of the potential deployment and economic and environmental sustainability assessments of similar technologies aiming at providing balancing services to the power grid and dispose of organic waste.

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In review

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In review

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Keywords: renewable energy power resources; SOFC; SOEC; biomethane production; waste valorisation; grid adequacy; hydrogen.

Abstract

A large market penetration of non-dispatchable renewable power sources (vRES), i.e. wind and photovoltaic, may be hampered by an increasing need for large scale energy storage capacity and challenges in power grid balancing. Novel technologies integrating waste gasification with reversible Solid-Oxide Cell (rSOC) systems are proposed to provide flexible grid balancing services. The rSOC system operated in electrolysis mode uses excess power from vRES to generate hydrogen (H₂) which is combined with syngas derived from waste gasification to produce methane (CH₄). The rSOC system can also be operated in fuel cell mode by oxidising syngas to produce electricity. In this work a methodology aimed at estimating the potential deployment of the rSOC technology in a future power system dominated by intermittent renewables is developed. The hourly power grid residual loads (i.e. the difference between load and vRES power generation) and the low-grade organic waste and residues availability, were quantified and matched for the southern Italian peninsula in 2030. The results show that the theoretical grid flexibility needs - about 10 TWh of overproduction and 5 TWh of underproduction in 2030 - might be fully satisfied with the complete disposal of the municipal organic waste generated in 2030 (6.7 Mt) and the production of 1.4–2.4 Mt of renewable CH₄, pointing to an intriguing perspective for the deployment of rSOC systems at large scale. The multifunctionality of the system proposed is an added value that can make it a convenient and efficient piece of the puzzle of technologies to invest in a climate-neutral and circular economy. The results and methods here presented are ultimately to be intended as the basis for the estimations of future potential deployment and economic and environmental assessments of competing technologies.

1 Introduction

39 The member states of the European Union (EU) have signed and ratified the Paris agreement to
40 keep global warming “well below 2 degrees Celsius above preindustrial levels, and to pursue efforts
41 to limit the temperature increase even further to 1.5 degrees Celsius”. To meet this challenging
42 target, the EU has put forward the ambitious Green Deal, a growth strategy that transforms the
43 Union into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy. Specific goals are (1) no net
44 emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050, (2) decoupling economic growth from resource use, and (3)
45 leaving no person and no place behind. The European Green Deal is the roadmap for making the
46 EU’s economy sustainable (European Commission, 2019).

47 Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions resulting from the provision of energy services have contributed
48 significantly to the historic anthropogenic climate forcing, impacting the energy budget of the
49 atmosphere. Since approximately 1850, global use of fossil fuels (coal, oil and gas) has increased to
50 dominate energy supply, leading to a rapid growth in emissions of climate forcers, e.g. GHGs
51 (Edenhofer et al., 2011). Demand for energy and associated services, to meet social and economic
52 development and improve human welfare and health, is increasing. All societies require energy
53 services to meet basic human needs and to serve productive processes. Historically, economic
54 development has been strongly correlated with increasing energy use and growth of GHG
55 emissions, and renewable energy can help decouple that correlation (Edenhofer et al., 2011).

56 In its EU2020 climate and energy package, the EU passed a directive on renewable energy in 2009:
57 The Renewable Energy Directive (RED) (European Parliament, 2009). The RED set targets for
58 renewable energy at 20 % by 2020. In November 2016, the European Commission published the so-
59 called winter package a set of measures part of the ‘Clean Energy for all Europeans’ initiative. A
60 recast of the RED was included in the package. In 2018, the EU has agreed on a set of ambitious
61 targets in its 2030 energy union strategy, with renewables expected to cover 32 % of the total
62 energy consumption (European Commission, 2018b). To reach such an overall renewable energy
63 target, in 2030 the EU needs to meet more than 50 % of its gross electricity generation needs, using
64 renewable energy sources (RES), as the power sector is easier (and cheaper) to decouple from fossil
65 fuels than other systems (e.g. transport) (Banja et al., 2017).

66 Variable/non-dispatchable renewable energy resources (vRES), namely wind and solar photovoltaic
67 (PV), have indeed grown over 4-fold in capacity in Europe between 2007 – 2016, from 62 GW to
68 260 GW (IRENA, 2019a), and are still increasing. Costs of RES technologies have been decreasing
69 abruptly, especially for solar PV and wind, which have resulted in high levels of competitiveness
70 for RES on a more levelized general power market (IRENA, 2019b). However, the large
71 penetration of intermittent, weather dependent vRES, poses serious threats on system operation,
72 such as increased interconnector flows, greater need for balancing and storage, as well as
73 curtailment of RES (Collins et al., 2018).

74 The large penetrations of vRES on some electric grids have resulted in increased levels of
75 curtailment in recent years. Studies of renewable energy grid integration have found that
76 curtailment levels may grow as the penetration of wind and solar energy generation increases (Bird
77 et al., 2016). Collins et al. (Collins et al., 2018) found that variable renewable curtailment increased
78 linearly beyond 20 % penetration of vRES and it is an inherent part of a highly variable renewable
79 power system. This is not only due to operational inefficiency but also to costs for additional
80 transmission infrastructure and storage system needed to avoid curtailment. This challenge may be
81 handled by assessing the trade-offs between trading with neighbouring countries/regions or adding
82 flexibility options, depending, case by case, on what is more secure and economically viable.

83 A wide spectrum of energy storage technologies are being evaluated as candidates for transferring
84 surpluses from the electricity grid to the gas grid or to a gas-consuming process. The importance of
85 power to gas technologies for handling high shares of RES and complying with the grid balancing

86 needs, rather than facing a future curtailment of generation, is being discussed at length (Götz et al.,
87 2016; Davies, J., Dolci, F., Klassek-Bajorek, D. and Cebolla, R., Weidner, 2020; Wulf et al., 2020).
88 Simonis and Newborough (2017) modelled the excess wind power in the Emden region of Germany
89 in the time period 2015-2020. The study was based on time series data for wind generation and
90 electricity demand, exhibiting that the excess renewable electricity levels will reach about 40 MW
91 and 45 GWh per annum by 2020, and concluded that it is desirable to achieve a progression in
92 power-to-gas capacity in the preceding period.

93 In this context, the rSOC technologies may play a pivotal role in the transition towards the
94 decarbonization of the power grid. The rSOC are system which can be operated in electrolysis mode
95 using excess power from vRES to generate H₂ or in fuel cell mode by oxidising a H₂ rich energy
96 carrier to produce electricity. As energy convertor, rSOC systems may enable the penetration of
97 large amounts of vRES in the power grid, by offering balancing services and producing renewable
98 fuels for the industrial, transport and heating and cooling sectors, which are the hardest to decouple
99 from fossil fuels. Hutty et al. (2020) presented successful proof-of-concept applications of rSOC
100 systems to microgrid real cases. They found that rSOC systems may reduce the import of grid
101 power and reach up to 50% of grid independence, whilst attaining cost-effectiveness.

102 Although various technologies exist to provide additional energy storage to the grid, each
103 technology mainly works in a distinct and strict time and energy capacity range (Olsen et al., 2020).
104 Indeed, energy storage systems based on rSOC technology present some key advantages in terms of
105 flexibility, adaptability, capability and efficiency, where more pronounced balancing needs are
106 observed. The rSOC systems boasts easy scalability (e.g. kW to MW) and can be used on hourly up
107 to monthly timescales. They can therefore be deployed at different locations, where they can either
108 store energy as fuels or chemicals or be connected to the natural gas grid. Round trip efficiency for
109 these types of system is close to 70 % and is envisaged it could raise up to 80 % (Peters et al., 2015;
110 Frank et al., 2018; Venkataraman et al., 2019). Furthermore, because of the solid feature of solid-
111 oxide stacks, there is limited risk of electrolyte leakage. On the other hand, in relation to fuel
112 utilization, still safety challenging issues exist, such as: risk of corrosion of materials, carbon
113 deposition and nickel oxidation; presence of impurities and gas cleaning; balance-of-plant (BoP)
114 modifications and/or new burner and heat exchanger installation. These issues are expected to be
115 resolved and/or fine-tuned to achieve a full integration of rSOC systems with gasifiers for their
116 large scale deployment (Liu et al., 2013).

117 In this work we propose a multifunctional system, named Waste2Grids (W2G) hereafter, resulting
118 from the combination of a rSOC system with a waste biomass gasifier connected to both the natural
119 gas and power grids (W2G Project). In a W2G system the H₂ is produced with a rSOC operated as
120 electrolyser, using excess power from vRES. The H₂ is then combined with syngas from biowaste
121 and residues gasification to produce synthetic CH₄. The rSOC system can also be operated in fuel
122 cell mode, by oxidising syngas to produce electricity.

123 CH₄ is considered as the final chemical product, due to its large-scale distribution, storage
124 infrastructures and applications. The amount of H₂ that could directly be injected to the gas grid is
125 limited by country specific standards and regulations to a maximum of 0-12 vol.% (Götz et al.,
126 2016; Biswas et al., 2020). On the contrary, synthetic CH₄ may exploit the existing natural gas
127 infrastructures for storage in large quantities over long periods of time (in Europe alone the storage
128 capacity is about 1 PWh, i.e. ca. 20 % of the total annual consumption) (GIE). Beside having a large
129 storage and distribution infrastructure already available, CH₄ is an optimal energy and carbon
130 carrier which can make RES available to a large portfolio of final uses due to its intensive
131 integration with other well-established natural gas sectors and facilities, i.e. mobility, as CNG motor
132 fuel, industry or space heating and cooling. Besides, showing an efficient combustion, natural gas
133 has low tailpipe or stack emissions, and, if used in fuel cells, it has virtually no emission of harmful

134 pollutants in the operation phase. On top of these positive aspects, this combination of biowaste and
135 residues gasification with the rSOC provides the added value of efficiently disposing and valorising
136 the organic waste, thus limiting the environmental impacts.

137 The Italian power market zones are investigated with the aim of identifying the areas with highest
138 penetration of vRES (i.e. vRES-dominated zone) and, therefore, remarkably in need of storage
139 capacity and flexibility in the power system. Based on historical data of vRES generation and load
140 in the Italian power market areas, and the planned penetration of intermittent renewables,
141 simulations of 2030 residual loads scenarios were calculated and matched with the biowaste
142 availability taking into account the efficiencies of a representative set of the novel W2G system, for
143 the quantification of its maximum technical potential deployment.

144 Beside the identification of the maximum W2G deployment potential, aim of this work is to make
145 publicly available the estimate of the hourly power grid balancing needs in 2030, estimated
146 according to the NECP projections, and the spatial distribution and availability of biowaste to
147 further studies.

148 **2 Materials and methods**

149 The overall goal of the W2G technology is to facilitate the penetration of vRES power in RES-
150 dominated areas and efficiently dispose of organic waste, by balancing the grid and synthesising at
151 the same time a renewable chemical. The first step is converting various types of carbon-containing
152 waste (e.g., industrial and municipal organic waste, secondary and tertiary biomass) into syngas - a
153 mixture of H₂/carbone monoxide (CO)/ carbon dioxide (CO₂) - via gasification. Then, the syngas is
154 cleaned and further conditioned (if necessary) to meet the requirements of the rSOC unit. It works
155 in solid-oxide fuel cell (SOFC) mode for power generation (PowGen) and in solid-oxide
156 electrolysis (SOEC) mode for power storage (PowSto). This two-mode operation, as defined in
157 W2G, requires the interaction with an electrical grid to capture the electricity storage and generation
158 needs. However, there might be certain periods of time when the amount of generated and
159 demanded power are close to each other, i.e. when the corresponding residual loads are limited. To
160 keep a continuous operation of the system, avoiding costly and inefficient shut down and start up
161 phases, a third operation mode, the power neutral mode, is introduced (PowNeu). In PowNeu mode,
162 the power produced internally in SOFC mode is also used internally to produce CH₄ in SOEC
163 mode. Thus, the plant can be considered as isolated from the electrical grid but remains under
164 operation, and can be back-in-service for the electrical grid in a short time, by switching from the
165 PowNeu mode to PowGen or PowSto modes.

166 The energy flows of the three modes are schematically shown in Figure 1. The gasification process
167 is considered to operate all the time, while the solid-oxide cell switches among the three operating
168 modes depending on the balancing scenarios to handle. In order to allow the operation of the three
169 modes in a single plant, the solid-oxide cell stacks are split into two blocks: Block A and B. Both
170 blocks can switch between SOFC (PowGen) and SOEC (PowSto) modes. The PowGen mode
171 converts the cleaned syngas from the gasification process into power with the fuel cell operation of
172 the solid-oxide cell stack (both Block A and B) and delivers the electricity produced to the grid. The
173 PowSto mode imports electricity from the grid and converts the syngas from the gasification
174 process into CH₄ with the electrolyser operation of the solid-oxide cell stack (both Block A and B)
175 and sends the CH₄ produced to the natural gas grid. In the PowNeu mode, a part of the syngas is
176 converted in the Block A (SOFC operation) into power to drive the Block B (SOEC operation), so
177 that the remaining syngas can be converted into CH₄. The overall process is exothermic with a
178 considerable amount of excess heat at the intermediate temperature levels, which can be used by an
179 additional steam cycle to enhance the efficiency of each mode. The technical concept and

180 thermodynamic performances of the W2G technology is described in more detail in (Wang et al.,
181 2020b).

182 **2.1 General methodology to assess the potential deployment of Waste2GridS systems**

183 The methodological approach adopted to estimate the technical potential deployment of the W2G
184 systems in 2030, includes three main tasks (Figure 2). In a first task an analysis of historical
185 disaggregated data is carried out to quantify the current dispatchable and flexible generation needs
186 (residual loads) in the different market zones with high vRES penetration, and the expected
187 development of residual loads in 2030, according to the expected penetration of wind and PV. In a
188 second, parallel task, a geographically explicit assessment of the available biomass in the selected
189 areas, as feedstock to support the deployment of the W2G technology, is performed. The last task
190 consists in the identification of the maximum potential deployment of the W2G technology, based
191 on the future availability of waste and residues and the expected theoretical balancing needs of the
192 power system, due to the higher penetration of vRES in 2030.

193 **2.1.1 Analysis of current and future power balancing needs**

194 The current and 2030 balancing scenarios were developed for the different electrical zones in Italy
195 in order to identify the optimal case study (see Section 3.1). They are based on statistical analysis of
196 historical/forecasted data, provided by the Italian Transmission System Operator (TSO) (Terna,
197 2019a). The expected data for the 2030 scenario were obtained by scaling the current power profiles
198 in Italy to the planned expectations for 2030, based on growth targets and trajectories for the
199 renewables share in the electricity sector, according to the Italian National Energy and Climate Plan
200 -NECP (Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico et al., 2019). The different zones were assumed to
201 increase proportionally to Italy as a whole. Table 1 reports the expected increase of RES penetration
202 in the time horizon 2016-2030 in Italy, provided by NECP.

203 The electricity grid balancing power profiles, approximated as dispatchable and flexible generation
204 needs, were defined in terms of residual loads, namely the imbalance between gross consumption
205 and vRES generation (the sum of wind and solar power generation in our case). The energy balance
206 of the electrical system is calculated on an hourly basis. Residual load is defined hour by hour as the
207 difference between the foreseen load (total electricity demand) and the production from vRES. A
208 positive residual load implies the need of energy sources other than PV and wind in order to fulfil
209 the grid requirements. A negative residual load occurs when the available vRES cannot be fully
210 absorbed by the grid, so the resultant overproduction would be curtailed or fed to a power storage
211 system. PowGen and PowSto modes of the W2G rSOC system would be then used to balance the
212 positive and negative residual loads, respectively.

213 In order to consider the substantial year-to-year fluctuation in climatological drivers, affecting wind
214 and solar PV capacity factors and generation trends, the current power generation profiles were
215 developed not using just a single year of generation data (e.g. 2017 or 2018), rather by calculating
216 the hourly inter-annual mean of capacity factors for PV and wind power profiles from 2011 to 2018
217 (2012 was not available), and applying the up-to-date installed capacity of 2018, to determine what,
218 to the purpose of the present study, is called the current vRES energy production. The use of the
219 averaged capacity factor values may lead up to peaks shaving and, consequently, to an
220 underestimation of the maximum capacity of the vRES system. Notwithstanding, this approach was
221 evaluated as the best compromise and a proper approximation to overcome the inadequacy of one
222 single year in depicting the inter-annual variability. Load profiles were elaborated accordingly. To
223 be noted, the inter-annual time-series were compared as a function of working and non-working
224 days, in order to consider the bias caused by the load reduction occurring systematically during
225 weekends.

226 As exemplification of data treatment, Figures 3 and 4 show the inter-annual variation of 2011 –
227 2018 (w/o 2012) historical data of capacity factors for wind and solar PV for two months, referring
228 to the selected electrical Italian zone (see Section 3.1) in Southern Italy; January and July were
229 reported as representatives of the cold and warm seasons. The green line indicates the averaged
230 values taken as current status to calculate power generation according to the installed capacity
231 reported for 2018.

232 Wind power production exhibits no clear diurnal pattern, but a favourable seasonal profile with
233 much more intensity and variation and a consequent higher production during the cold season. Solar
234 PV is characterized by its typical daily pattern, with multi-peaks daily trends with higher intensity
235 in the middle of the day and steep changes in concomitance with sunrise and sunset, as well as a
236 higher contribution in the warm season.

237 The current hourly-based generation profiles and the electrical load patterns were generated for the
238 entire annual timescale. The dataset was then scaled to 2030 based on the targets provided by NECP
239 (Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico et al., 2019), to identify the expected residual loads in 2030.
240 The applied increase coefficients were assumed, in comparison to 2018 installed capacity,
241 as 222.7 %, 276.5 % and 102.1 %, for wind, PV generation and load, respectively.

242 **2.1.2 Biomass assessment**

243 In combination with the evaluation of the grid balancing needs in 2030, we performed the
244 characterization and the quantification of biomass availability to fuel the W2G technology. There
245 are many biomass classifications scheme available worldwide.

246 The scheme adopted in this work for biomass classification was developed in the frame of the EU
247 projects Biomass Energy Europe (BEE - <https://www.eu-bee.eu/>), which had the scope of
248 harmonising the methodologies for biomass resource assessments for energy purposes in Europe
249 and its neighbouring countries. While the biomass assessment follows the approach proposed by the
250 EU S2Biom Project (<https://www.s2biom.eu/>). The biomass resources are therefore evaluated as
251 follows:

- 252 • Energy crops: wood energy crops (short rotation forestry, i.e. willow, eucalyptus, poplar),
253 grass energy crops (miscanthus, hemp), oilseed crops (rape, linseed, sunflower), hydroponics (lake
254 weed, kelp algae);
- 255 • Wood, wood residues and by-products: wood and wood branches from forest, wood residues
256 from the industrial sector (sawmills, construction, furniture);
- 257 • Agricultural residues: wheat or barley straw, corn stover, pruning (fruit, vineyard);
- 258 • Livestock: pig and cattle slurry, sheep manure, grass silage, poultry litter;
- 259 • Agro-industrial residues: residues and waste from various processes in the distillery, dairy,
260 meat, fish, oils, fruit and vegetable sectors;
- 261 • Waste: sewage sludge, organic fraction of MSW.

262 Taking into account the technology investigated and the characteristics of the examined areas, the
263 following biowaste categories were considered:

- 264 i) Agricultural residues: cereal straw, fruits tree pruning;
- 265 ii) Waste: MSW organic fractions, waste wood and waste paper.

266 The Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT, a), reports the annual grains and fruits
267 production and their cultivated areas at EU NUTS 2 level (European Commission, 2018c). The
268 annual straw and pruning computed at NUTS 2 level were subsequently allocated on NUTS 3 level,
269 by using the Italian Agriculture Census (ISTAT, b) as proxy, enabling to obtain higher spatial
270 resolution at Italian municipalities scale. Straw and pruning residues were then quantified by
271 applying specific empirical conversion factors, taken from (ENAMA, 2011), to the annual
272 production of grain and fruits.

273 MSW data are provided by the Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA)
274 (ISPRA. Waste database:), the public Italian authority in charge of waste management monitoring,
275 which elaborates the annual MSW report, a database containing quantitative data on all the fractions
276 of the MSW at NUTS3 level. The 2018 report was considered (reference year 2017) and three
277 different MSW fractions - i.e. organic, paper and wood – were quantified for the municipalities of
278 interest. MSW quantification for the year 2030 was performed according to the mandatory goals set
279 by the Waste Directive (EU) 2018/851 (European Commission, 2018); the MSW was therefore
280 considered as separated at origin in its organic fraction.

281 Annual straw, pruning, waste paper, waste wood and MSW data were elaborated and then
282 computed by employing the Q-GIS (Quantum Geographical Information System) software and
283 raster algorithms (QGIS, 2020), with the aim of producing a georeferenced dataset of a spatial
284 explicit distribution of organic waste availability. The georeferenced datasets ensure data
285 interoperability, Standard Query Language (SQL) query capabilities, and dynamic visualization.

286 The ratio underpinning this short list is that the gasification technology, though it may work with
287 many more types of feedstock, is more reliable and efficient with low moisture feedstock (Sikarwar
288 et al., 2016). On top of that, dry feedstocks are easier to be transported and stored. We also focus on
289 low grade waste streams, as hypothetically these will suffer from less competition from other uses,
290 in a future bio-based economy, and have a lower, and in some cases a negative, cost.

291 Environmental aspects have also contributed to the identification of the feedstocks considered.
292 Fruits tree pruning are often burned in the field, causing the emissions of air pollutants. Cereal
293 straw, though it may be considered a residue, provides benefits to the soil health, ecosystem
294 services and stores carbon out of the atmosphere (Giuntoli et al., 2016; Serra et al., 2017) Energy
295 crops are excluded for their competition for agricultural land (European Commission, 2015) and the
296 environmental impacts they generate with the large use of machinery, fertilisers and pesticides
297 (Agostini et al., 2015, 2020).

298 Forest biomass is excluded as well. Though several sources consider the net annual increment
299 (NAI) of the forest biomass as available for bioenergy production, at least partially (e.g. both
300 Biomass Energy Europe Project; S2Biom Project), we focus on low grade residual biomass. On top
301 of that, the appropriation of the forest NAI for bioenergy production, releasing instantaneously the
302 carbon in the atmosphere, cannot be considered carbon neutral, but rather as foregone sequestration
303 (Pan et al., 2011; Maxwell et al., 2019).

304 Manures are excluded for their moisture content and difficult and costly handling, transport and
305 storage.

306 **2.1.3 Potential deployment**

307 In order to be able to assess whether the amount of residual biomass and waste estimated for the
308 2030 scenario would be sufficient to cover the full grid balancing needs of the examined area, the
309 efficiency of the W2G system is needed.

310 There are a set of degrees of freedom for the design of W2G plants, e.g. the technology combination
311 (gasifier type, syngas cleaning technology, stack technologies, steam turbine network, etc.) and
312 operating conditions of the key components, particularly the stacks. All these aspects were
313 considered by Wang et al. (Wang et al.) with the implementation of an optimization platform to
314 derive a set of optimal plant designs (design pool). They show the trade-off between mode-
315 efficiency (i.e. PowGen, PowSto) and capital expenditure (CAPEX), or specific cell area per kW-
316 LHV of the processed biomass (Wang et al., 2020b, 2020a). Five options were finally shortlisted
317 from the pool of the optimal designs. These five options are considered sufficient to enable a good
318 coverage of the overall characteristics of the W2G technology. The energy content of the biomass
319 needed as input to produce the specified amounts of electricity or CH₄, and the corresponding
320 efficiency values in PowSto and PowGen modes are reported in Table 2.

321 The energy content of the available feedstocks was quantified by applying the same lower heating
322 values (LHV) used by the European Commission for the calculation of the default values of the
323 RED (Giuntoli et al., 2017).

324 By combining the waste availability and process design efficiencies, we have identified the
325 constraints to the deployment of the W2G technology, in terms of maximum power utilisation in the
326 PowSto mode and in the PowGen mode.

327 **3 RESULTS**

328 In this section the results of the biowaste availability, power grid balancing needs, and potential
329 deployment of the W2G technology are reported. To be noted, all these estimates represent the
330 technical sustainable potential, they do not account for competition with other uses of the biomass
331 and waste, as these will depend on the economic performances of the technology and markets and
332 policies, which are not accounted for in this work. Furthermore, they do not account for the
333 potential use of other technologies for the stabilisation of the power grid or the connectivity with
334 other power markets to dispose of the excess power from vRES.

335 **3.1 Identification of vRES-dominated areas and of future dispatchable and flexible power** 336 **generation needs**

337 A peculiarity of the Italian system is the zonal management of the electricity market that reflects
338 grid limitations in transmission capacity. The stretched shape of the Italian Peninsula, dominated in
339 the middle by Apennines, a mountain chain extending from North-West to South-East bordered by
340 narrow coastlands, limits the possibility to achieve a full meshed grid integration, especially
341 between North and South of Italy. The Italian electricity market has therefore a zonal structure in
342 which the zones are defined as parts of the National power grid where physical limits exist for
343 electricity transfers to/from other geographical areas. The six geographical zones of the national
344 network are shown in Figure 5: Northern Italy (NORD), Central-Northern Italy (CNOR), Central-
345 Southern Italy (CSUD), Southern Italy (SUD), Sicily (SICI) and Sardinia (SARD). Therefore,
346 although in a future perspective more investments on the grid are expected to help increase the
347 flexibility of the overall system, reducing curtailments and local congestion, the short to mid-term
348 deployment of local storage systems can play an important role to drive the transition to high-vRES
349 scenarios (Terna, 2019b).

350 In Italy, at the end of 2017, the installed capacity of wind and solar PV was about 9.8 GW and 19.7
351 GW, corresponding to 17.2 TWh and 24.4 TWh of electricity generation, respectively, representing
352 a total renewable energy penetration of 12.5 % and expected to increase over years. The NECP
353 envisages a central role for vRES in the future Italian power energy mix, with PV expected to
354 account for more than a half of the power capacity by the end of the decade, (i.e. 50 GW installed

355 capacity by 2030). In the NECP projections, RES totalize an electricity generation of 186.8 TWh,
356 including 74.5 and 40.1 TWh of PV and wind power, respectively. The 2018 data provided by
357 TERNA - the Italian TSO in charge for high voltage electricity transmission networks and the
358 auxiliary services market throughout the country - were explored and disaggregated into the six
359 market zones. The 2018 renewable penetration rate for wind and PV power was 5 %, 10 %, 16 %, 27 %, 28 % and 54 %, in NORD, CNOR, CSUD, SARD, SICI and SUD, respectively (Ministero
361 dello Sviluppo Economico et al., 2019).

362 Figure 6 shows the distribution of the PV and wind power installed capacity in Italy, at the level of
363 provinces and regions, respectively. Most wind power plants (more than 95 %) are located in the
364 south of Italy, while solar PV plants are distributed more uniformly throughout the country, with a
365 slight higher contribution in northern regions. In terms of power generation, the higher productivity
366 of the PV plants in the South, thanks to more than 2000 hours of sunshine estimated per year, is
367 counterbalanced by a higher number of proper sites for distributed generation in the North (e.g. civil
368 and industrial building roofs). However, Northern regions, being more densely populated and
369 industrialized, exhibit a much less pronounced overproduction from RES (Guandalini et al., 2017);
370 pointing to Southern areas as more impacted by transmission congestion and energy curtailments in
371 a future perspective.

372 A recent analysis of the Italian authority for the power system management shows that vRES
373 penetration has already determined an increasing wind curtailment in Italy. In 2019, the wind power
374 energy curtailment was estimated at 606,7 GWh, (3% of the total wind production), whose 62% is
375 concentrated in the South of Italy (ARERA 321/2020/I/EFR, 2020).

376 The Italian lockdown, which took place in spring 2020 due to the Covid-19 pandemic, can be
377 considered a sort of real-scale laboratory experiment of the expected conditions of the electricity
378 system in 2030. In fact, according to preliminary estimations (ENEA, 2020), wind curtailment
379 could have reached ca. 60 GWh in the single week 27 April – 3 May 2020, corresponding to 10% of
380 the total wind curtailment in 2019, and pointing out to important warning signals in terms of
381 adequacy of the future power system.

382 This is reflected by our 2030 power grid balancing scenarios. Figure 7 shows hourly-based residual
383 loads patterns for SUD, the zone exhibiting the highest negative residual loads. The plots refer only
384 to two months, i.e. January and July, reported as representative of the cold and warm seasons. They
385 show that a low frequency of positive residual loads and a large overproduction of vRES power, are
386 expected (i.e. flexibility needs dominated by PowSto), without significant seasonal fluctuations. In
387 SUD, indeed, the influence of heating and lightning requirements during winter is counterbalanced
388 by cooling systems consumption during summer, resulting in a limited annual variation of
389 electricity demand. Table 3 reports our estimations, calculated from the same dataset, of hours in
390 overproduction for 2030 in Italy. They evidence a much more pronounced overproduction for SUD
391 with respect to the other zones, corresponding to a large increase in installed non-dispatchable RES
392 capacity which drives a strong mismatch between production and load. This points to not negligible
393 storage requirements in the time horizon 2020 – 2030, with large capacity combined with rapid
394 charge/discharge periods, that can potentially be matched by the W2G technology.

395 Molise, Puglia, Basilicata and Calabria, the four regions being part of the SUD zone, were therefore
396 identified as the main RES-dominated Italian areas and SUD was selected as the case study for this
397 work.

398 **3.2 Residual biomass availability in 2030**

399 The amount of biomass, available to be converted to syngas to enable the operation of the W2G
400 technology in the RES-dominated zone SUD, was quantified by building a Geographical
401 Information System (GIS) geodatabase that spatially covers the areas identified as the power market
402 zone SUD (i.e. the regions Molise, Puglia, Basilicata and Calabria) and the region Campania. The
403 neighbouring region of Campania was added for the biomass availability quantification, because of
404 the high potential of municipal solid waste (MSW) production of Naples and its surrounding area
405 and their lack of disposal capacity (i.e. issues experienced with illegal waste disposal and export to
406 other regions) (Triassi et al., 2015; Ripa et al., 2017). The georeferenced database was used as input
407 to evaluate the feasibility of the proposed technology and to size the future plants with the scope of
408 balancing the 2030 electricity grid by recycling waste, taking into account its 2030 targets in
409 compliance with the RED recast (European Commission, 2018) directive and the EU Circular
410 Economy package (European Commission, 2018).

411 The agricultural residues include cereals straw and fruits trees pruning, as these ones are identified
412 as the most relevant agricultural residues in the selected southern regions. SUD presents a total area
413 of 62,531 km², of which 17,550 and 9,962 km² are covered by cereal crops cultivation and fruit
414 trees plantation, respectively.

415 For the regions under evaluation, the crops chosen for the straw biomass availability assessment are
416 Wheat, Barley, Oat, Rice, Corn and horticulture. These crops cultivation areas amount to 1,755,020
417 ha. The fruit trees with more relevant production in the selected regions are olives, vineyard,
418 peaches, apricot, cherries and oranges, for the reference year 2018, totalling an area equal to
419 996,234 ha.

420 The sustainability standards for agricultural forestry and land management deriving from the
421 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) (European Commission, 2018a) were taken into account to
422 elaborate the 2030 projections for agricultural farming practices, land management and agreed
423 (national and regional) forestry management plans.

424 The CAP sustainable agricultural farming practices include applying conservation of Soil Organic
425 Carbon (SOC) practices (e.g. Cross Compliance issues of ‘maintaining agricultural land in good
426 farming and management condition’ and avoiding soil erosion). Moreover, there may be market
427 constraints, as the straw is already used for livestock bedding, animal feed and, in perspective,
428 biorefineries, building biomaterial and 2nd generation biofuel (ENAMA Biomass Project -
429 <https://www.enama.it/progetto-biomasse/sccc7227d>). Therefore, as regards straw, in order to
430 account for the impact on soil health, ecosystem services, storage of carbon into the soil and the
431 competition with other markets, only a conservative 30 % of the total straw production was
432 considered available in 2030.

433 Fruit trees pruning currently has a limited use. They can be used for conventional combustion.
434 However, given the very high moisture content (about 60%), high bark and ashes content, low
435 spatial density (2-4 t.d.m./ha), and the high collection, bailing and transport costs, they are not
436 competitive on the market. Currently pruning are mainly chopped and left in the fields, or burned to
437 preserve fruits trees from infection (Enama - Biomass Project) . The real limitation for the year
438 2030 exploitability is the feedstock market price, in case of pruning for syngas conversion, as no
439 major environmental constraints are present. For the year 2030, base potential is considered 90% of
440 the potential calculated for 2018.

441 The 2030 waste stream availability was estimated based on demography projection and the goals
442 contained in the Circular Economy Package Directive (European Commission, 2018).

443 Figures 8 A, B, C, D and E shows georeferenced maps of the waste and residues availability
444 expected in 2030, of pruning, straw, waste paper, waste wood and MSW, respectively. Figure 8 F
445 shows the total waste and residues availability for gasification in a W2G plant in 2030.

446 The potential obtained is thus considered as the sustainable technical potential (Figure 9). It does
447 not include any economic aspect, in particular, regarding alternative uses of the same feedstocks
448 within a future European bioeconomy. While this methodological approach tends to overestimate
449 the availability of waste and residues, limiting the waste and supply area to the region under
450 analysis has an opposite impact on estimates, as it excludes potential imports. Residues (and waste
451 in particular) are often transported for long distances, e.g. a large percentage of the waste produced
452 in the Central and Southern regions of Italy are treated in plants located in the Northern regions,
453 indicating a national movement of waste from South to North (Malinauskaite et al., 2017).
454 Transboundary transport is rather common as well, in extraordinary cases large amounts are
455 transported between countries (The New York Times. A Whiff of Naples Arrives in Hamburg
456 (2008)). Thus, in the framework of this study, authors referred to the technical potential to account
457 at least for the current sustainability constraints, refraining from any economic analysis and market
458 and policy issues, such as comparisons with the future competing uses. In fact, the georeferenced
459 organic waste stream database and the power grid data are made available online (W2G Project).

460 Table 4 provides the total technical potential of residues and waste available for SUD in 2030 and
461 the corresponding energy content. To be noted, the energy content refers to the dry part of the
462 biomass. This approach reflects the limited impact of water content on gasification processes, on the
463 contrary of combustion, where the moisture content of the fuel is determinant. For the year 2018,
464 the maximum technical potential of straw was estimated at 2,754,612 t.d.m./year, while the
465 maximum technical potential of pruning at 1,356,780 t.d.m./year.

466 **3.3 Potential deployment of Waste2GridS technology in the Italian case study**

467 The maximum potential installed capacity was identified for the RES-dominated zone SUD, both in
468 PowGen and PowSto modes.

469 Tab. 5 presents the results obtained by comparing the residual loads expected in 2030, with the
470 maximum power capacity of the W2G technology, which can be matched by the biomass waste and
471 residues available (Table 4) in those regions. The five different best performing designs - D1, D2,
472 D3, D4 and D5 - and the corresponding efficiencies were taken into account (Table 2). Data are
473 reported in terms of availability of biomass with respect to the energy needs for the two examined
474 modes of operation, i.e. PowGen mode and PowSto mode, for SUD. The total waste availability is
475 the total energy content of waste and residues, expressed in MWh.

476 Biomass needs PowGen is the amount of biomass required as gasification feedstock to fuel the
477 PowGen operation required to balance the power grid. Biomass need PowSto shows the total
478 amount of biomass needed to produce the amount of syngas required to match the amount of excess
479 electricity in the power grid, to stoichiometrically produce CH₄ to be injected into the gas grid. The
480 Total biomass need corresponds to the sum of Biomass need PowSto and Biomass need PowGen.

481 If the total biomass need is larger than the total biomass availability, this would imply a surplus of
482 biomass and the only constraint to the W2G technology deployment can be considered the
483 flexibility needs of the power grid. The Cells in red highlight the cases in which the residues and
484 waste are not sufficient to cover fully the balancing and flexibility demand of the power grid.

485 Histograms in Fig. 10 show the frequency and capacity of hourly balancing needs for the power
486 grid system analysis in 2030 (A), and the cumulative residual load in terms of power consumption

487 or production (B). The cumulative residual load represents the potential operation of W2G systems
488 in PowGen and PowSto modes, to fully satisfy the dispatchable and flexible generation needs of the
489 power grid.

490 In PowGen mode, the amount of available biomass satisfies the energy demand for all the
491 configurations. The biomass availability is not a constraint to operate the PowGen mode, and the
492 local biomass would be able to balance the excess electricity in the power grid in SUD. The same is
493 in PowSto mode for D1, D2, D3 and D5, whereas, the amount of biomass is sufficient to run a
494 maximum capacity of 4225 MW in PowSto mode, D4. These results correspond to a production of
495 renewable CH₄ in the range 1.4 – 2.4 Mt. The total biomass required to balance the power grid in
496 both modes of operation is considerably higher and the amount of biomass potentially available in
497 2030, resulting not enough in D1 and D4 designs.

498 Results of the methodology applied in this work shows that incorporating the 2030 expectations of
499 wind and solar power penetration into the existing electricity system in SUD, would result in large
500 and frequent surpluses and deficits attributable to the patterns of vRES variability. In order to
501 satisfy the magnitude of the surplus and deficits, corresponding in total to ca. 5.5 and 9.4 TWh,
502 respectively, a 4025 and 6600 MW of maximum potential installed capacity were identified, when
503 the system is operated as PowGen and PowSto, respectively.

504 **4 Discussion**

505 W2G systems are rSOC combined with the gasification of waste and residues. The overall approach
506 of the system is conceived in the perspective to provide grid-balancing flexible services, with the
507 ability to fulfil upward and downward power adjustments, being able to operate both as SOFC and
508 SOEC.

509 The scope of this work was to estimate the potential role of W2G system in fulfilling the power grid
510 balancing needs in 2030.

511 In the first step of the analysis, the 2030 dispatchable and flexible power generation needs generated
512 by the high penetration of intermittent, weather dependent, vRES were quantified in Italy. The
513 power market zone SUD was identified as a RES-dominated zone.

514 In the second step, the low grade residual biomass availability in the same area was quantified.

515 In the third, and last step, the power grid balancing need were matched with the biowaste
516 availability by taking into account the efficiencies of optimised W2G systems.

517 Based on statistical high resolution historical data and a plausible estimation of power generation
518 and load in 2030, this work provides the characterization of specific power grid balancing needs and
519 a detailed georeferenced biowaste availability assessment, in order to explore the maximum
520 potential capacities of the W2G technology both in power storage mode and power generation
521 mode.

522 In power storage mode the W2G system uses excess power from vRES combined with syngas from
523 waste gasification to produce CH₄, to be injected in the natural gas grid for transport and storage.
524 This operational mode is a key asset of the technology as it offers a multiplicity of added values:

- 525 • it allows a higher penetration of renewables by absorbing the excess power which can cause
- 526 grid unbalances or renewables power generation curtailment;
- 527 • it produces an energy and carbon carrier which has already a large distribution network and
- 528 storage capacity;

- 529
- it can provide long term seasonal storage of the excess renewables power;
- 530
- it produces an energy carriers which may be used to decouple from fossil fuels all sectors of
- 531
- the economy (transport, space heating, industry and others);
- 532
- it contributes to solve the issue of organic waste disposal.

533 In power generation mode the syngas produced from waste is used as SOFC to produce renewable
534 power, and dispose of organic wastes and residues.

535 On top of that, the reversibility of the plant enables the continuous operation, which improves the
536 efficiency and economics, by avoiding both the unproductive phases and the ramp up and down (or
537 warming and cooling) time of single mode power generation or storage technologies.

538 We found that the amount of waste and residues in the examined Italian regions can be enough to
539 match the power storage balancing need of the power grid. Analogously, as regards the power
540 generation mode, the residues and waste resulted sufficient to generate all the electricity need by the
541 power grid with most design configurations.

542 The potential for the deployment of the W2G technology is impressive, with an order of
543 magnitude of the rSOC capacity up to about 4 and 7 GW when the rSOC is operated in power
544 generation and power storage modes, respectively. The operation of the W2G systems would
545 correspond to about 5.5 TWh of power generated and 9.6 TWh of power absorbed from the grid,
546 and about 1.4–2.4 Mt of methane produced; while, at the same time, disposing of 6.7 Mt of
547 biowaste. In good agreement with our estimate, at least as order of magnitude, the Italian TSO, in
548 its adequacy analysis of the NECP scenario, reports projections of a need of about 6 GW additional
549 centralized storage capacity, mainly in the south, for 2030 (Terna, 2019c). These potentials are
550 theoretical upper limits to the deployment of the W2G systems, merely the technical sustainable
551 potential of biowaste and power grid estimated balancing needs were considered.

552 **5 Conclusions**

553 The power sector is one of the main contributors to global warming, and RES may play a key role
554 in its decarbonization. The transition towards a climate neutral energy system requires higher
555 penetration of vRES, namely wind and PV. The EU aims at achieving a 96-99% renewable energy
556 share in power sector by 2050 (EU energy roadmap 2050). This paper proposes a case study for the
557 deployment of the novel W2G rSOC system in the so called RES-dominated area in Italy, to enable
558 such a renewable penetration in the power sector.

559 The results showed that the power overproduction from intermittent renewables may be an
560 opportunity instead of an issue. The W2G technology is a win-win-win technology: it may dispose
561 of all the organic waste of a RES-dominated zone; it may fully balance the power grid, also in the
562 long term (summer-winter); it may produce valuable renewable fuels (i.e. syngas, H₂ and CH₄) and
563 a chemical building block for the other sectors of the economy (transport, space heating, industry).

564 The research question underpinning the methodology proposed in this work was ‘what is the
565 potential deployment of the W2G technology’. To answer that question, the two other questions to
566 answer were ‘what is the balancing need of the power grid in 2030?’ and ‘what is the availability of
567 biowaste in 2030?’. A methodological approach apt at answering those questions is presented. The
568 same approach can be applied to other areas characterized by overproduction of vRES and indeed
569 potentially interested in the application of similar technologies to balance the power grid and
570 dispose of the organic waste.

571 This work thus contributes to the understanding of what are the biowaste availability and power
572 sector features so as to support the identification of implementing policy measures enabling the
573 achievement of the overall EU energy targets. Moreover, beside the methodological approach, the
574 datasets on waste flows availability and power grid balancing needs published with this work may
575 represent the basis for similar studies and/or market/techno-economic optimization modelling.

576 To be highlighted, the results presented are considered sustainable technical potential, they are not
577 meant to represent the optimal solution, but rather to set a constraint to the maximum potential
578 deployment of the technology itself and support the identification of the optimal design and sizing,
579 operating parameters and location of this, or W2G-like technologies treating biowaste or balancing
580 the power grid. Indeed, this case study does not aim at providing a resolute prospective for the
581 application of the rSOC technology for the transition towards a 100% renewable energy power
582 sector in Italy, as economic and political aspects driving wholesale prices and total system costs of
583 the power grid are not accounted for.

584 **Conflict of interest**

585 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
586 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

587 **Author Contributions**

588 A.A.,L.W.,M.P.,Y.Z. and S.Y. involved in funding acquisition, designed the research Project and
589 the overall methodology; C.C., A.A. and F.G. analysed power generation and load data; N.P. and
590 V.M. performed the biomass assessment in Italy; C.C. and A.A. wrote the paper. All authors
591 contributed to the final review and editing.

592 **List of non-standard abbreviations**

593 LHV: Low Heating Value

594 PowGen mode: Power Generation mode of the rSOC

595 PowNeu mode: Power Neutral mode of the rSOC

596 PowSto mode: Power Storage mode of the rSOC

597 PV: photovoltaic

598 RED: Renewable Energy Directive of the European Parliament

599 RES: renewable energy resources

600 RES-dominated zone: areas characterized by high penetration of renewable energy resources

601 rSOC: reversible Solid-Oxide Cell

602 SOEC: Solid-Oxide Electrolysis Cell

603 SOFC: Solid-Oxide Fuel Cell

604 t.d.m.: tons of dry matter

605 TSO: Transmission System Operator

606 vRES: non-dispatchable renewable energy power resources

607 SUD: The identified RES-dominated zone for Italy, including four political regions in the South of
608 Italy (Basilicata, Calabria, Molise, Puglia)

609 W2G: Waste2GridS Project/Technology

610 **Data availability statement**

611 The waste stream and power grid (renewables and consumption) datasets were generated and
612 analysed for this Italian case study and can be found in the ZENODO repository at: 1)
613 <https://zenodo.org/record/3629527#.X-x-v9hKiUk>; 2) <https://zenodo.org/record/3625882#.X-x-1dhKiUk>.

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- 758 Wulf, C., Zapp, P., and Schreiber, A. (2020). Review of Power-to-X Demonstration Projects in
759 Europe. *Front. Energy Res.* 8, 1–12. doi:10.3389/fenrg.2020.00191.
- 760

761 Table 1. Italian electric energy mix for RES, in terms of installed capacity (MW) and electricity
 762 production, normalized according to the Directive 2009/28/CE, source: NECP (Ministero Italiano
 763 dello Sviluppo Economico, 2019).

	2016		2017		2025		2030	
	Inst. capacity (MW)	El. prod. (TWh)	Inst. capacity (MW)	El. prod. (TWh)	Inst. capacity (MW)	El. prod. (TWh)	Inst. capacity (MW)	El. prod. (TWh)
<i>Hydro</i>	18641	46.2	18863	46.0	19140	49.0	19200	49.3
<i>Geothermal</i>	815	6.3	813	6.2	920	6.9	950	7.1
<i>Wind</i>	9410	16.5	9766	17.2	15950 (300 off-shore)	31	19300 (900 off-shore)	41.5
<i>Bioenergy</i>	4124	19.4	4135	19.3	3570	16	3760	15.7
<i>Solar-PV</i>	19269	22.1	19682	24.4	28550 (250 CSP)	40.1	52000 (800 CSP)	73.1
<i>RES share (%)</i>		34.0%		34.1%		42.6%		55.0%

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765

766 Table 2. Thermodynamic performances for the five optimal plant designs selected. The energy
767 content of the biomass is considered as 50104 kW (LHV) in input for all the five designs (Wang et
768 al.).

Design options	Electricity produced [kW]	PowGen eff [%]	Electricity consumed [kW]	Methane produced [kg/s]	Power stored in methane [kW]	PowSto eff [%]
<i>1</i>	21862	43.6	24287	0.84	41959	56.4
<i>2</i>	23756	47.4	48533	1.36	67836	68.8
<i>3</i>	25149	50.2	47692	1.36	67836	69.4
<i>4</i>	25564	51.0	19044	0.77	38588	55.8
<i>5</i>	26986	53.9	49638	1.36	67879	68.1

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In review

771 Table 3. Summary of overproduction in the different zones of the Italian electrical power system,
772 according to TSO data and our projections. *The multiannual scenario refers to the current scenario,
773 i.e. the hourly inter-annual mean from 2011 to 2018 (2012 was not available). The electrical zones
774 are geographically visualized on the map of Fig.5.

Hours in Overproduction			
Zones	2018	Multiannual hourly average	2030
<i>SUD</i>	1240	350	4715
<i>SICI</i>	1	0	1498
<i>SARD</i>	200	0	1659
<i>NORD</i>	0	0	4
<i>CNORD</i>	0	0	102
<i>CSUD</i>	0	0	119

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In review

777 Table 4. Technical potential of the feedstock in 2030.

Feedstock		availability in 2030 (t)	moisture % *	Energy content LHV (MJ/kg dry)**	Energy content (kWh of the dry part)
<i>Agricultural residues</i>	Pruning	1,221,102		18.0	6,105,510
	Straw	826,384		17.2	3,948,279
<i>Municipal Solid Waste - MSW, separated at origin</i>	Organic	3,721,023	50	20.7	10,697,941
	Paper	796,697	10	18.0	3,585,137
	Wood	86,110	10	18.0	387,495
	total				24,724,362

778 * average, from (TNO, 2020)

779 ** (Giuntoli et al., 2017)

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In review

781 Table 5. Comparison between the residual loads and the local (in-around SUD) biomass waste and
 782 residues availability, in terms of energy content, by adopting W2G technology in the five proposed
 783 designs. The cases in which the biomass is not sufficient to fully balance the residual loads are
 784 highlighted in red.

	Design 1	Design 2	Design 3	Design 4	Design 5
<i>biomass need PowSto (GWh)</i>	19,485	9,750	9,922	24,849	9,534
<i>biomass need PowGen (GWh)</i>	12,697	11,684	11,037	10,858	10,286
<i>tot biomass need (GWh)</i>	32,182	21,435	20,960	35,707	19,819
<i>total biomass available (GWh)</i>	24,724	24,724	24,724	24,724	24,724
<i>% tot need / tot available</i>	130%	87%	85%	144%	80%
<i>PowSto / tot available</i>	79%	39%	40%	101%	39%
<i>PowGen/tot available</i>	51%	47%	45%	44%	42%

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In review

809 Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the energy flows of the three modes for W2G plants. The red
810 arrows stand for energy flows related to biomass fed into the plant and the syngas generated from
811 the gasification processes; the green arrows represent power/electricity flows; the blue arrows
812 indicate energy flows related to water and steam; the purple arrows are the energy flows related to
813 the CH₄ produced. The rSOC stacks are split into two blocks - Block A and Block B, to allow for
814 the operation of the three modes in one single plant; GASI: gasification; FC: fuel cell operation;
815 EC: electrolyzer operation; ST: power storage. The figure is only a simple illustration and does not
816 represent a detailed flowchart.

817

818 Figure 2. Exemplification of the methodology adopted in this work to determine the potential
819 deployment of the W2G systems in specific RES-dominated areas.

820

821 Figure 3. Statistics of 2011 – 2018 (w/o 2012) historical hourly based data of capacity factors for
822 PV (A) and wind (B) corresponding to January (cold season).

823

824 Figure 4. Statistics of 2011 – 2018 (w/o 2012) historical hourly based data of capacity factors for
825 PV (A) and wind (B) corresponding to July (warm season).

826

827 Figure 5. Zones in the Italian electricity system (adapted from (Terna, 2019b)).

828

829 Figure 6. Distribution of the installed capacity for wind (A, 2018) and PV (B, 2019) power.

830

831 Figure 7. The total variable renewable generation (PV and wind) and residual load (hourly-based) in
832 January (A) and July (B) for the RES-dominated regions in Italy, namely the SUD zone as here
833 defined. Expected scenarios in 2030.

834

835 Figure 8. Georeferenced maps of 2030 projections, technical potential for (A) pruning, (B) straw,
836 (C) wood, (D) paper, (E) municipal organic waste, and (F) total feedstocks availability.

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838 Figure 9. Biomass potential classification, adapted from (S2Biom Project).

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840 Figure 10. Frequency histogram of the hourly PowGen/PowSto power capacity (A). Energy content
841 of waste and residues needed to support the W2G technology deployed in the vRES-dominated
842 zone (B). 2030 scenario in Southern Italy (SUD zone).

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Residual Loads Frequency - SUD (2030)

Cumulative Residual Loads - SUD (2030)

